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COSMIC: Workshop briefing paper

Use of new media in crisis situations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY [EN]

This briefing paper provides an overview of the key findings from the completion of three reports relating to the use of new media in crisis situations that have been completed as part of the COSMIC project. COSMIC, “Contribution of Social Media in Crisis management”, is a two-year project that is funded under the European Commission's Seventh Framework Programme FP7-SEC-2012 under grant agreement no. 312737.

The first report, D2.1, identified existing information communication technologies (ICTs) and new media applications that being used for crisis management purposes. Key lessons learned include:

- Stakeholders should focus on the capabilities of different ICTs to meet their communication needs in preparing for, responding to and recovering from a crisis.
- Different applications have different functionalities and can be accessed using different means. There is no “one size fits all”, rather, stakeholders should consider their individual needs in different types of crises and utilise the appropriate applications to meet those requirements.
- There is currently a lack of publicly available information to fully understand the extent to which different stakeholders are using different types of new media applications.

The second report, D2.2, included an analysis of the use of ICTs and new media applications in eight scenario case studies involving different types of crisis in Europe and Internationally. Key findings include:

- Some scenarios, e.g., the UK heat wave (2013) demonstrated that the value of social media is limited, whilst in others it is a valuable tool to aid crisis management, showing that the type and nature of the crisis matters when considering the use of social media in crisis management activities.
- There is a shortage of publicly available information evaluating the usefulness of social media following a crisis by public authorities.
- There is, at times, a high risk of miscommunication and misuse of social media in a crisis.
- The news media can contribute to crisis management efforts via their engagement with social media.
- The use of social media should not replace traditional communication systems, but rather, supplement them.

The final report, D2.3, examined the adverse use and reliability of new media. Key findings include:

- The adverse use of new media applications during a crisis includes; improper use of infrastructure, misinformation and disinformation, which can significantly impact the reliability of the use of new media in a crisis.
- New media may be intentionally or unintentionally misused in a crisis. The report highlights the different sources and types of misuse of ICTs.
- While trying to respond to potential misuses of information, various stakeholders, including government authorities, may themselves hinder the effective use of new media technologies for crises communication.
- Stakeholders appear to be taking measures to manage and verify the information they receive, yet, further developments in technology are required to help improve verification practices to ensure the reliability of information.

The findings from each of these reports will be taken into consideration throughout the duration of the project and will feed into the development of guidelines for citizens, government authorities, first responders and industry for the most effective use of ICTs to aid the security of citizens during a crisis.

This briefing paper serves as a brief overview to be used as preparatory reading for two stakeholder engagement workshops that will be held in February 2014, in Greece and the Netherlands. Further information about the COSMIC project and its activities can be found on the project website:

<http://www.cosmic-project.eu/>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY [NL]

COSMIC, over de "*Bijdrage van Social Media in crisis management*", is een tweejarig project dat wordt gefinancierd via het 7^e kaderprogramma van de Europese Commissie (FP7-SEC-2012 GA no. 312737.) In dit document vindt u een overzicht van de belangrijkste bevindingen met betrekking tot het gebruik van nieuwe media in crisissituaties, zoals die zijn weergegeven in de drie tot nu toe opgeleverde rapporten.

Het eerste rapport (D2.1) gaat in op bestaande informatie-en communicatietechnologieën (ICT) en "nieuwe media" toepassingen die worden gebruikt voor crisisbeheersing. Belangrijke bevindingen zijn:

- Om te voldoen aan de communicatiebehoefte bij de voorbereiding op, bestrijding van en herstel uit een crisissituatie, moeten betrokkenen zich richten op de mogelijkheden van verschillende ICT toepassingen.
- Verschillende applicaties hebben verschillende functies en zijn op verschillende manieren toegankelijk. Er is geen "one size fits all" oplossing, maatwerk is nodig waarbij de eigen behoefte van betrokkene en de eisen die een specifiek incident stelt, bepalend moeten zijn voor de gekozen toepassing(en).
- Er is in het openbare domein onvoldoende informatie beschikbaar om een goed inzicht te krijgen in de al in gebruik zijnde "social media" toepassingen bij organisaties die betrokken zijn bij de crisisbeheersing.

Het tweede rapport, D2.2, heeft betrekking op acht case studies en bevat een analyse van het gebruik van ICT en "nieuwe media" in uiteenlopende crisomstandigheden binnen en buiten Europa. De belangrijkste bevindingen uit dit onderzoek zijn:

- Soms, bijvoorbeeld bij de hittegolf in het Verenigd Koninkrijk (2013) blijkt de waarde van sociale media beperkt te zijn, terwijl het in andere gevallen een waardevol instrument is om hulp te bieden. Hieruit blijkt dat type en aard van de crisis van belang zijn bij de overweging sociale media in te zetten bij crisis management .
- Er is met betrekking tot het nut van de inzet van sociale media bij crisissituaties door de overheid, onvoldoende publiekelijk beschikbaar evaluatiemateriaal.
- Er is soms bij crisomstandigheden een hoog risico op miscommunicatie en misbruik van sociale media.
- Reguliere nieuwsmedia kunnen via hun betrokkenheid bij sociale media goede bijdragen leveren aan crisisbeheersing.
- Het gebruik van sociale media is geen vervanging voor de traditionele communicatiesystemen , maar eerder een aanvulling erop.

Het laatste rapport, D2.3, beschrijft het nadelige gebruik en de betrouwbaarheid van de nieuwe media. Belangrijkste bevindingen zijn:

- Onjuist gebruik van de infrastructuur, mis- en desinformatie kunnen de betrouwbaarheid van het gebruik van nieuwe media in een crisissituatie ernstig beïnvloeden.
- Nieuwe media kunnen opzettelijk of onopzettelijk misbruikt worden in een crisis. Het rapport belicht de verschillende bronnen en vormen van misbruik van ICT.
- Bij hun pogingen om te reageren op potentieel misbruik van informatie belemmeren diverse betrokkenen, waaronder de overheid, zichzelf bij het effectief gebruik van nieuwe media technologieën voor crisiscommunicatie .
- Betrokkenen lijken al maatregelen te nemen om de betrouwbaarheid van de door hen ontvangen informatie te verifiëren, maar verdere technologische ontwikkelingen zijn nodig om de controleerbaarheid van informatie te vergroten en daarmee de betrouwbaarheid te verbeteren.

De bevindingen van elk van deze rapporten zullen gedurende de looptijd van het project worden gebruikt bij de ontwikkeling van richtlijnen voor burgers , overheden , hulpverleners en industrie voor het meest effectieve gebruik van ICT om de hulpverlening aan de burgers te verbeteren tijdens een crisis.

Dit document dient als een kort overzicht om te worden gebruikt als voorbereiding op twee workshops die in februari 2014 zullen worden gehouden in Griekenland en Nederland. Verdere informatie over het COSMIC project en onze activiteiten is te vinden op de website van het project : <http://www.cosmic-project.eu/>

ΣΥΝΟΠΤΙΚΗ ΠΑΡΟΥΣΙΑΣΗ

Αυτό το ενημερωτικό έγγραφο παρέχει μια επισκόπηση των βασικών συμπερασμάτων από την ολοκλήρωση τριών εκθέσεων σχετικά με τη χρήση των νέων μέσων ενημέρωσης σε καταστάσεις κρίσης που έχουν ολοκληρωθεί ως μέρος του προγράμματος COSMIC (<http://www.cosmic-project.eu/>). Το COSMIC είναι ένα διετές πρόγραμμα με τίτλο: «Η συμβολή των Κοινωνικών Μέσων Ενημέρωσης (Social Media) στη διαχείριση κρίσεων», που χρηματοδοτείται από το Έβδομο Πρόγραμμα Πλαίσιο FP7-SEC-2012 της Ευρωπαϊκής Επιτροπής βάσει της σύμβασης με αριθμό 312737.

Η πρώτη έκθεση, D2.1, προσδιόρισε τις υπάρχουσες τεχνολογίες πληροφορικής και επικοινωνιών (ΤΠΕ) και εφαρμογές νέων μέσων που χρησιμοποιούνται για λόγους διαχείρισης κρίσεων. Τα βασικά διδάγματα είναι:

- Οι ενδιαφερόμενοι θα πρέπει να επικεντρωθούν στις δυνατότητες κάλυψης των επικοινωνιακών αναγκών τους μέσω διαφορετικών ΤΠΕ κατά την προετοιμασία, τη διάρκεια και την επαναφορά από μια κρίση.
- Διαφορετικές εφαρμογές έχουν διαφορετικές λειτουργίες και μπορούν να προσεγγιστούν χρησιμοποιώντας διαφορετικά μέσα. Δεν υπάρχει πανάκεια και οι ενδιαφερόμενοι θα πρέπει να εξετάσουν τις ιδιαίτερες ανάγκες τους σε διαφορετικούς τύπους κρίσεων και να αξιοποιήσουν τις κατάλληλες εφαρμογές για την κάλυψη αυτών των απαιτήσεων.
- Υπάρχει επί του παρόντος έλλειψη διαθέσιμων πληροφοριών στο κοινό για να κατανοήσουμε πλήρως την έκταση στην οποία τα διάφορα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη χρησιμοποιούν διαφορετικούς τύπους των εφαρμογών νέων μέσων.

Η δεύτερη έκθεση, D2.2, περιελάμβανε την ανάλυση της χρήσης των ΤΠΕ και των εφαρμογών νέων μέσων σε οκτώ μελέτες περιπτώσεων που αναφέρονται σε διαφορετικά είδη κρίσης στην Ευρώπη και διεθνώς. Βασικά ευρήματα είναι τα εξής:

- Ορισμένα σενάρια, για παράδειγμα το κύμα καύσωνα του Ηνωμένου Βασιλείου (2013), έδειξαν ότι η αξία των Κοινωνικών Μέσων Ενημέρωσης (ΚΜΕ) είναι περιορισμένη, ενώ σε άλλες περιπτώσεις είναι ένα πολύτιμο εργαλείο για την ενίσχυση της διαχείρισης των κρίσεων, που δείχνουν ότι το είδος και η φύση της κρίσης έχει σημασία κατά την εξέταση της χρήσης των ΚΜΕ στις δραστηριότητες διαχείρισης κρίσεων.
- Υπάρχει έλλειψη διαθέσιμων πληροφοριών στο κοινό για την αξιολόγηση της χρησιμότητας των ΚΜΕ μετά από μια κρίση από τις δημόσιες αρχές.
- Υπάρχει, κατά καιρούς, υψηλός κίνδυνος προβληματικής επικοινωνίας και κακής χρήσης των ΚΜΕ σε μια κρίση.
- Τα μέσα ενημέρωσης μπορούν να συμβάλουν στις προσπάθειες διαχείρισης των κρίσεων μέσω της εμπλοκής τους με τα ΚΜΕ.
- Η χρήση των ΚΜΕ δε θα πρέπει να αντικαθιστούν τα παραδοσιακά συστήματα επικοινωνιών, αλλά μάλλον, να τα συμπληρώνουν.

Η τελική έκθεση, D2.3, εξέτασε την δυσμενή χρήση και αξιοπιστία των νέων μέσων ενημέρωσης. Βασικά ευρήματα περιλαμβάνουν τα εξής:

- Η δυσμενή χρήση των νέων μέσων ενημέρωσης κατά τη διάρκεια μιας κρίσης περιλαμβάνει, την ακατάλληλη χρήση υποδομών, και την παραπληροφόρηση, η οποία μπορεί να επηρεάσει σημαντικά την αξιοπιστία της χρήσης των νέων μέσων σε μια κρίση.
- Τα νέα μέσα επικοινωνίας μπορούν να καταχραστούν είτε εκούσια είτε ακούσια σε μία κρίση. Η έκθεση υπογραμμίζει τις διαφορετικές πηγές και είδη κατάχρησης των ΤΠΕ.
- Ενώ προσπαθούν να ανταποκριθούν στις ενδεχόμενες καταχρήσεις των πληροφοριών, διάφορα εμπλεκόμενα μέρη, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των κυβερνητικών αρχών, μπορούν οι ίδιοι να εμποδίζουν την αποτελεσματική χρήση των νέων μέσων ενημέρωσης στην αντιμετώπιση μιας κρίσης.
- Τα εμπλεκόμενα μέρη φαίνεται να λαμβάνουν μέτρα για τη διαχείριση και την επαλήθευση των πληροφοριών που λαμβάνουν, όμως, περαιτέρω εξελίξεις στη τεχνολογία απαιτούνται που θα συμβάλουν στη βελτίωση των πρακτικών ελέγχου με σκοπό την εξασφάλιση της αξιοπιστίας των πληροφοριών.

Τα παραπάνω ευρήματα θα ληφθούν υπόψη στη διάρκεια του έργου και θα τροφοδοτήσουν την ανάπτυξη κατευθυντήριων γραμμών προς κάθε εμπλεκόμενο μέλος κατά τη διάρκεια μιας κρίσης.

INTRODUCTION

The world of communication and information technology is developing at a vast rate. This is a threat as well as an opportunity for risk and crisis managers in government and industry. There are currently a host of existing and emerging new media applications that can contribute to crisis management activities, however, their perceived effectiveness is less clear. Accordingly, this briefing paper provides an overview of the key findings from the completion of three reports relating to the use of new media in crisis situations that have been completed as part of the COSMIC project. COSMIC “Contribution of Social Media in Crisis management” is a two-year project that is due to end in March 2015. COSMIC has seven multi-disciplinary partners, and is funded under the European Commission's Seventh Framework Programme FP7-SEC-2012 under grant agreement no. 312737.ⁱ

The aims and objectives of the project include:

- To explore new and emerging communication technologies and applications and provide an insight into the most effective ways to utilise them to promote the enhanced safety and security of citizens in crisis situations.
- To assist better communication and information gathering for authorities and first responders.
- To examine the potential roles and ethics regarding citizen participation in emergency response.
- To produce guidelines that will assist authorities and first responders in deploying new and emerging communication technologies and applications to better protect citizens in crisis situations.

Figure 1: The COSMIC project

STATE OF THE ART OF NEW MEDIA IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Effective communication is a critical component of crisis management and plays a key role during the preparation, response and recovery of a crisis.ⁱⁱ

As reported in Deliverable 2.1 of the COSMIC project, the tools with which communication can take place has expanded from conventional information communication technologies (ICT) such as the telephone and radio, to a host of new media applications.ⁱⁱⁱ This does not mean that conventional ICT's are redundant, but instead are no longer the sole means of providing up-to-date information to, and communicating with affected citizens in an emergency.

New media is distinct from conventional ICT in a number of features; it is made up of digital content, which is made up of data, text, image and sound that can be distributed across networks. New media is inherently social, enabling users to communicate and share these various digital objects to many users across the globe.

Figure 2: New media

STATE OF THE ART IN COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY FOR CRISIS MANAGEMENT

The availability of ICT for crisis management includes, among others, traditional forms of communication including landline telephone, radio, printed press and television. These systems are being supplemented by digital ICT's. Within crisis management, there are critical and basic/important functional requirements that are required from ICT's, examples include: critical functionality such as two-way (voice) communication and text messages. Basic, yet important, functionality includes: group voice communications, image, video and document transmission. These are further supplemented by additional capabilities, which help to contribute to crisis management efforts, examples include: verification of biometric data, document scan and transmission, access to digital maps, database access and check etc. Thus, ICTs are no longer solely concerned with the transmission of voice or text based information, but are able to contribute to other types of sharing and communication abilities that can significantly contribute to the efforts of managing a crisis. In addition to providing different functions, ICTs must also have non-functional requirements, including for instance: to be available, reliable, resilient, cost-effective etc. Please see the Appendix for further information regarding the functional and non-functional requirements of ICT in crisis response.

LESSON LEARNED: 1

In the past, ICTs have been viewed as “products”, instead, attention should be placed on the capabilities of different systems, for ICTs can be developed in conjunction with other components and services that can be used or further developed to help meet the communication needs of those involved in crisis management.

STATE OF THE ART IN NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT

The widespread availability of new media applications provides visual information and the ability to enable users to interact and share information with others. These applications range from social networking websites to tailor-made crisis management tools and applications. **Combined, these tools provide stakeholders with the opportunity to co-ordinate and collaborate to respond to emerging crises, as well as to prepare for future incidents.** Partners analysed the functionality of 31 new media applications that were recognised as having been used in crisis management activities in past incidents. Functionality was assessed according to their primary “type” of function, their main functionalities and how users could access them (*see figure right*). Examples of applications examined include: Twitter, Facebook, Google Crisis Response Apps, American Red Cross Apps, Ushahidi, AMBERalert, European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre, Earthquake, NL Alert etc.

Figure 3: Categorisation of applications

Social networking sites offer stakeholders a unique combination of functions, in particular, with a way of communicating and sharing digital content in real-time, across multiple devices. Many of applications are available to use via the web and mobile applications. A central feature is their ability to connect global networks of existing and emerging social relations, providing extensive opportunities for the more effective and integrative management of crises across different stakeholders groups.

Web tools and crowdsourcing applications include specific tools and platforms that stakeholders can use for different purposes in responding to and managing crisis. They are less focused around communication and social networks and more focused on providing a service that multiple users can contribute to (e.g., mapping a crisis). It is important to note that the applications that are based around crowdsourcing activities rely on

individuals forming like-minded networks for the applications to be of use to respond and manage a crisis and thus social networking applications are complementary.

Mobile tools are often tailor made, and require users to download and install applications on their mobile devices for later use. Many applications are designed to be used by individuals whilst they are mobile, thereby ensuring, in the first instance, that their functions (e.g., alert mechanism) contribute to securing citizens safety in the event of a crisis. The interoperability of applications, including social networking sites make them useful tools under some circumstances, however, some applications are aligned to particular types of crises and are subsequently an additional application available to users rather than one that is utilised by individuals on a routine (e.g., daily) basis.

Access to applications: Whilst some applications could be used via a variety of means, others were restrictive in the ways in which users can access them; the most popular form was the mobile applications category (30 applications), and the least popular was the SMS utility of applications (5 applications).

Functionality of applications – key findings

- 30 out of 31 were capable of performing one-way communication.
- 28 out of 31 were capable of assisting stakeholders with organisation efforts in a crisis.
- 13 out of 31 were able to allow users to request and offer assistance.
- 1 out of 31 was only able to offer users the ability to seek assistance.
- 10 out of 31 enable individuals to relay (share) information.
- 7 out of 31 allowed for two-way communication; thereby expanding the abilities of different stakeholders to communicate in a crisis.

Figure 4: New media applications by function

It is evident that applications provide different functionality that may or may not be suitable for responding to a crisis. It is important to note that the findings suggest that a “one size fits all” approach does not apply to the use of new media applications in crisis situations. Rather, stakeholders should consider their individual needs in crises as well as the nature of the crisis and utilise the appropriate applications to meet those needs.^{iv}

LESSON LEARNED 2.

Different applications have different functionalities and can be accessed using different information communication technologies. There is no “one size fits all”, rather, stakeholders should consider their individual needs in different types of crises and utilise the appropriate applications to meet those needs.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS & USAGE TRENDS

Due to the lack of publicly available “usage” information for some applications, it is difficult to know which stakeholders are using new media applications as part of their preparation, response and recovery to a crisis.

Based on the information that was available, the summary (*right*) of stakeholder usage has been observed. Notably, of the “known” usage, civil society organisations seem to be more likely to engage with the various types of new media applications than other stakeholders, particularly those in industry and the media. It is necessary for researchers to further understand what applications stakeholders are using to broaden their insights of the effectiveness of future efforts in using new media as

	Social networking	Web tools	Crowdsourcing	Mobile tools	Total
Government	3	3	3	0	9
Media	3	2	3	0	8
CSO's	5	5	4	0	14
Industry	3	3	2	0	8
Public	5	2	3	1	11
Unknown	0	2	0	11	13

part of crisis management activities. To do so, it is necessary for stakeholders using new media, as well as developers of new media applications to take the adequate legal measures to share usage data.

Table 1: Known stakeholder usage of applications for crisis management

LESSON LEARNED 3.

Whilst there are many functions that different telecommunications and new media applications are able to offer, their usefulness is dependent on stakeholders using them to meet their needs in crisis management activities. Understanding “usage” and “engagement” with new media applications is crucial to enhancing efforts in optimally utilising new media as part of crisis management activities. In order to fully understand what tools stakeholders are using, further research is required.

CASE STUDY SCENARIOS ON USE OF NEW MEDIA IN A CRISIS

COSMIC examined a series of eight case study scenarios of different types of crises in order to explore the ways in which new communication technologies and applications were being used in crisis situations today.^v

Figure 5: COSMIC D2.2 case studies

Conventional communication technologies

In the majority of cases, conventional communication technologies (e.g., (mobile) telephone, fax, television- and radio broadcasting) were used by the public and authorities to tackle some of the challenges that the crises posed. Partners noted that conventional technologies proved to remain integral to our lives in a crisis. The overall conclusion of the examined case studies showed that it is still early days to consider relying on either conventional or new communication technologies as the only communication channel and crisis management tool during a crisis. Examples of the use of conventional communication tools include: during the 2013 U.K. heatwave the Met Office transmitted warnings via email and the web to various organisations, who would then use e-mail, the Internet, SMS messaging systems, television and radio broadcasts to disseminate warnings and health-related information to agencies and members of the public. Elsewhere, during the U.K. floods (2012) a Floodline (telephone line) was opened for the public to be able to find out whether they were at risk of flooding. Eligible residents were also able to sign up to Floodline Warnings Direct, a free service that sends direct messages, by telephone, mobile, email, SMS text message or fax, when flooding is expected.

There were also examples of problems with conventional communication systems. For instance, during the 2013 Boston marathon attacks, officials argued that landlines and cell phones would have been unreliable as both telephone systems were rendered largely inoperable due to the overloaded demand, and thus, new media proved to be a valuable communication tool. Elsewhere, following the earthquake in Haiti (2010), the use of conventional technologies for communicating after the earthquake was impossible, at least during the first few hours after the earthquake. As soon as the local infrastructure was repaired, information was broadcasted to survivors on how best to use their mobile phones to respond to the situation.

LESSON LEARNED 4.

Telecommunications infrastructures and services may suffer outages during a crisis, therefore, simultaneous use of traditional and new technologies is required for authorities and other stakeholders to be able to reach as much part of the affected population as possible.

New communication technologies

New communication technologies offer an advantage over traditional methods and can help response agencies provide their services more efficiently and effectively to the public, as well as potentially reach a larger portion of the population. In all case studies, social media was used by a variety of stakeholders, ranging from state and local authorities, to response organizations and members of the public. To illustrate:

- Following the Boston attacks, new communication technologies were used extensively. Authorities responded to the bombings, with the use of interoperable radio hardware, an Emergency Patient Tracking software tool and the Wireless Emergency Alert system (WEA). Each of these systems offered improvements on previous information and communication tools that authorities had at their disposal like landline telephones and cell phones which turned out to be unreliable as a result of overload.
- During the U.K. heatwave more established means of communication were used by the authorities to spread messages about the heatwave and the associated health risks.
- In the aftermath of the earthquake in Haiti new technologies were used in various ways. Haitians could use SMS to report missing persons, shelter problems and food issues, while the service also sent SMS texts with important information to registered users. Skype was also used by international mainstream media organisations to interview survivors.
- During the Gezi Park protests new technologies (e.g., Whatsapp) were mostly used by the public as a means of communication e.g., to provide real-time coverage the protests.
- New communication technologies played a significant role in the response to Hurricane Sandy, ranging from modern two-way radio deployments, through to mobile telephony technology, to novel web applications. WEA was also utilized by FEMA, to alert citizens of the incoming storm.

New technologies did not always produce positive results as was the case in the Colorado wildfires case study where one of the Emergency Notification Systems (ENS) failed to work properly during the fire. This resulted in evacuation notifications either sent to the wrong addresses or not sent to the population that should have evacuated the area in danger.

LESSON LEARNED 5.

Social media can act as a counterbalance when conventional warning systems fail to operate. Therefore, authorities should not neglect to monitor and update their social media pages regularly.

Functionality of new media applications

New media applications have different functions, which should be respected when stakeholders try to determine what application to use for different purposes.

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)

In most cases, social media was used as a form of one-way communication between various stakeholders and the public. Social media was used to alert the public of the imminent crisis and to advise them on how to prepare for it as well as recover after it was over. In the aftermath of the Boston bombings, the authorities used social media to publicise suspect photos, share information about the bombing and announce the arrest of a suspect. Elsewhere, following the 2013 heatwave in the UK, authorities used social media to alert the population of the occurrence of the heatwave and during the U.K. floods of 2012. In other cases, such as the Colorado wildfires, social media was used by several businesses to inform their clients of current conditions concerning themselves and the situation in general.

2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)

In all case studies, with the exception of Xynthia, where local authorities either did not have social accounts or did not use them, and the Gezi protests, where authorities did not use social media, stakeholders tried to not only inform but also to solicit information from the public regarding the crisis at hand. For example, after the Boston bombings, the authorities requested that members of the public, who were present at the event, share images or video footage that they recorded. Later on, the FBI released the images of two suspects and solicited public help in naming them. Elsewhere, during the U.K. heatwave UK Power Networks broadcasted information about power outages, and solicited information about power outages and vulnerable individuals from members of the public. The information being shared via social media after the Haiti earthquake often included urgent messages such as reports of injuries or of trapped people, as well as expressing important needs for instance regarding food and shelter in response to authorities' use of social media.

3. Request/offer assistance

Social media was also used in some cases either by authorities and organisations to offer assistance or by members of the public to request assistance. Many organisations monitored social networks during hurricane Sandy and were able to respond according to the information they were receiving from individuals. During the Gezi protests, following a survey of citizens' use of social media, 13% of the respondents indicated that by learning about the events via social media as to where police were organised, and where people were being injured, they could mobilise and provide assistance to the protestors. Haitians also used social media, predominantly Twitter, to communicate with each other and ask for assistance.

4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)

In all of the case studies social media was used by the public to relay information posted online by the different stakeholders participating in the crisis management process. In some cases the public were aware of the need to relay potentially vital information. During Gezi protests, people who used Twitter for gathering and sharing information constituted the largest segment with 47% of the survey's respondents. 20 million Tweets were sent out regarding hurricane Sandy but we do not know the percentage of those which were actual retweets of an original tweet. The Colorado wildfires showed that people need to be reminded to re-share information. Tweets and posts by authorities were rarely shared while posts by a local news agency were re-shared hundreds of times. In their original post the agency urged people to share the information they provided.

5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)

In several cases social media was used for campaign purposes. In Haiti for example, organisations turned to social media to raise donations. During the Gezi protests, Tweets were oriented towards raising public awareness about police misconduct. After the Xynthia storm, Facebook was used for campaigning for

support to the victims as well as raising awareness about the government's plans of demolishing houses in "black areas".

6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)

Crowdsourcing after the Haiti earthquake helped organise first responders to deal with needs according to relevance and urgency. During the Gezi protests social media were used for coordination and organisation purposes. During the U.K floods Facebook was used to organize the public and recruit volunteers.

Risks

The examination of case studies revealed a series of risks and shortcomings to consider in the use of new media applications for crisis management activities. These include: rumour spreading (e.g., Hurricane Sandy), the occurrence of vigilante activity (e.g., Boston attacks), the sharing of unreliable information and other types of misuse. Further information regarding the issues associated with misuse and the reliability of information is discussed in the next sub-section.

LESSON LEARNED 6.

Key lessons learned from the case studies include:

- Social media is used by a range of different types of stakeholders in a crisis.
- Organisations should take the time to establish a social media strategy in the absence of a crisis to build their community network and to support their on-going preparation and risk communication activities.
- Different types of messages are relevant to different audiences. Organisations should consider the kinds of information that is most desired by an online audience, at different points in time, and for different sectors of the public.
- Officials and crisis responders should agree upon unique, intuitive hashtags prior to major events in order to facilitate information sharing and avoid significant amount of extraneous information, including advertisements, personal commentary and international information.
- Social media usage can be aggregated to discover information not present in individual messages.
- Social media can be used to correct misinformation being circulated by members of the public and to share breaking news with the mass media.

RELIABILITY & MISUSE OF NEW MEDIA

The correct use of new media application is of crucial importance in crisis response. However, ICTs and new media applications, particularly social media, may often be, intentionally or unintentionally, misused in ways that can impede efficient communication during a crisis or spread false information. This section will summarize findings from the *COSMIC Report on the adverse use and reliability of new media* (D2.3) regarding the types of misuse of new media.^{vi} Misuse of ICTs and new media can generally be categorised as 1) misuse involving improper utilisation of infrastructure; 2) misinformation/disinformation. The following figure provides further information as to these different categories of misuse.

Figure 6: Improper use of ICTs

As the examples to types of misuses of ICTs involving improper use of infrastructure suggest, various players, including hackers, government authorities, private corporations and citizens, may be involved in misuse of ICTs, as “misusers”, “victims”, or “responders”. It should also be noted that the distinction between “misuse” and response to misuse is often blurred. For example, activities of hackers may often be needed to help expose abuse of power. Notably, government authorities may have conflicting motivations: 1) protect the political authority and 2) protect the public good. The conflict between these two motivations become all the more relevant in political crises when government agencies may respond to what they consider, or frame, as adverse use of ICTs by pushing for the complete shutdown of all telecommunications infrastructures or enhanced surveillance of citizens. In a crisis context, the fact that national agencies, and private companies working on their behalf, can have access to enormous sets of data that record detailed information of users’ activities without their knowledge and consent may have important consequences for democratic rights such as freedom of association and freedom of speech.

LESSON LEARNED 7.

The ease with which information about individuals flows across national borders make it increasingly difficult for individuals to protect their privacy. Involvement of supranational organizations in protecting communicational privacy of individuals may be needed to shield individuals, and private corporations, from misuse by national governments.

Partners identified four types of misinformation and disinformation in the use of media in a crisis: misrepresentation, rumour spreading, propaganda and scamming.

Figure 7: Misinformation and disinformation

LESSON LEARNED 8.

Actors involved in emergency response need to actively monitor social media to identify and correct misinformation that are related to their functions and furthermore, pre-empt fraudulent activities that may be linked to their organization. Social media monitoring services that use techniques such as natural language processing to identify opportunities and threats for an organisations may also be helpful for key stakeholders to identify and correct false information efficiently.

RELIABILITY OF INFORMATION IN NEW MEDIA

Individuals' and organisations' increased access to online publication platforms along with the increasing use of social media as a source of information is changing the way Internet users learn about events and the unfolding of crisis. In part, as a result of the types of misuses described above (e.g., propaganda, rumour spreading) extended reliance on social media platforms increases the likelihood that unverified, and potentially false, information can circulate widely before being confirmed or rejected by reliable sources. In the past, the news media had the potential to alleviate the problem of misinformation by filtering false information. However, as a result of having to compete with a vast number of online information sources, the news media have skipped information verification steps to beat their competitors in terms of breaking the story, and has consequently contributed to the circulation of unverified and, often false information. At

the same time, new media have brought new and potentially more effective tools for both individuals and news organization to verify information using crowdsourcing, which can process effectively large quantities of data in digital format. Various tools such as Friend of a Friend (FOAF) project, Ushahidi, Checkdesk etc. provide users and journalists to engage in collaborative efforts to verify information sourced from new media applications.

Analysis of social media usage patterns during the Gezi Protests in Turkey indicate that types of information verification techniques that individuals use can broadly be divide into two categories: 1) “investigative approaches,” and 2) “convenience approaches”, within which users rely on methods that are already available to them to evaluate the reliability of information or passively wait for others to verify information. Collaborative methods, such as checking information with people who are first-hand witnesses are among the most frequently used methods. However, there is very little indication that these tools are utilized systematically by individuals.

Figure 8: Investigative vs. convenience approaches to information verification

LESSON LEARNED 9.

Crowdsourcing applications have already proven beneficial in the context of crises prompted by natural or political events. However, their full use will depend on whether they can reach a critical mass of users (both sources and readers). Interoperability of such crowdsourcing applications are key to achieving this goal.

CONCLUSION

This briefing paper has provided a brief overview of the role of new media in crisis situations. Further information can be found in the project deliverables which are available on the COSMIC website. Key points include:

- There are a host of new media applications (e.g., social networking sites, web based tools, crowdsourcing applications and mobile based applications) available to those involved in crisis management activities that supplement traditional ICT's by providing users with a number of additional functionalities that facilitate the sharing of information in a variety of digital forms ranging from voice, text, images, video etc.
- Different applications have different functionalities and can be accessed using different information communication technologies. There is no “one size fits all”, rather, stakeholders should consider their individual needs in different types of crises and utilise the appropriate applications to meet those needs.
- There is a distinct lack of open knowledge concerning the extent of the use of different new media applications by stakeholders for the purpose of crisis management.
- Examining past “use” of new media in crisis situation is valuable in highlighting best practices in utilising new media in a crisis. In future, stakeholders should ensure they consider the practice of reflection and identifying and sharing lessons learned from their experiences of using new media in crisis management.
- Whilst there are benefits of using new media in crisis situations there are also important considerations required in terms of the reliability of information stemming from the use of new media as well as other challenges relating to misinformation, disinformation and the improper use of infrastructure.

APPENDIX: FUNCTIONAL & NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS OF ICT IN CRISIS RESPONSE

	Functional Requirements										Non-Functional Requirements										
	Critical					Important-to-normal					Critical		Important-to-normal		Preparation						
	Basic and important					Examples of high-impact services/apps															
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Two-way radio (analogue)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Two-way radio (digital)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Satellite phone	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Amateur radio	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Broadcast radio	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Analogue television	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Digital television (as evolving)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Land-line telephone	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Web (Internet, website)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Smart phones (3G+)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Feature phones (2.5G+)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
GSM/cell phones (2G)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Analogue wireless phones (1G)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Key: (FRs) ✓: ok, p: possible, empty cell: not possible/not applicable; (NFRs) ++: good, +: ok, empty cell: average/borderline, -: poor, --: bad

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